

Treball de Fi de Màster

**Màster Universitari en Sistemes i
Accionaments Elèctrics**

**Distributed Multiport Converters for
Renewable Energy Integration**

REPORT

Author: Marc Solagran Jufre
Supervisor: Oriol Gomis Bellmunt
Co-supervisor: Paula Muñoz Peña
Call: July 2024

Escola Tècnica Superior
d'Enginyeria Industrial de Barcelona

Resum

Aquest treball de fi de màster investiga el paper dels convertidors multiport (MPCs) en la millora de la resiliència i l'eficiència de les xarxes de distribució. La recerca se centra en la reducció de l'energia no subministrada (ENS) i en com aquests poden facilitar la integració de recursos energètics distribuïts (DER) a la xarxa. Utilitzant com a banc de proves el sistema de 33 busos de l'IEEE 33 modificat, s'han realitzat simulacions per avaluar el rendiment dels MPCs sota diversos escenaris, incloent-hi fallades simples i dobles de línia i modes d'operació *grid-forming* i *grid-following* de les unitats de generació distribuïda (DG).

Tot i que en el cas base el rendiment elèctric de la xarxa de distribució ja és acceptable, l'estudi revela que els MPCs milloren significativament el rendiment de la xarxa, especialment en la regulació de voltatge i la reducció de pèrdues. L'anàlisi de la viabilitat econòmica indica que els MPCs d'escala parcial proporcionen una solució més rendible per a la millora del rendiment de la xarxa respecte a aquells a escala total. A més, la recerca avalua el potencial d'ingressos de la participació de sistemes d'emmagatzematge d'energia amb bateria (BESS) en els mercats elèctrics, destacant els beneficis de la participació al mercat diari i el de serveis auxiliars. Els resultats donen suport a l'adopció dels MPCs com una estratègia viable per a modernitzar les xarxes de distribució per a acomodar la creixent integració dels DER i facilitar aconseguir els objectius de sostenibilitat en l'àmbit energètic.

Resumen

Este trabajo de fin de máster investiga el papel de los convertidores multipuerto (MPCs) en la mejora de la resiliencia y la eficiencia de las redes de distribución. La investigación se centra en la reducción de la energía no suministrada (ENS) y en cómo estos pueden facilitar la integración de recursos energéticos distribuidos (DER) en la red. Utilizando como banco de pruebas el sistema de 33 buses del IEEE 33 modificado, se han realizado simulaciones para evaluar el rendimiento de los MPCs bajo diversos escenarios, incluyendo fallas simples y dobles de línea y modos de operación *grid-forming* y *grid-following* de las unidades de generación distribuida (DG).

Aunque en el caso base el rendimiento eléctrico de la red de distribución ya es aceptable, el estudio revela que los MPCs mejoran significativamente el rendimiento de la red, especialmente en la regulación de voltaje y la reducción de pérdidas. El análisis de la viabilidad económica indica que los MPCs de escala parcial proporcionan una solución más rentable para la mejora del rendimiento de la red en comparación con aquellos de escala total. Además, la investigación evalúa el potencial de ingresos de la participación de sistemas de almacenamiento de energía con batería (BESS) en los mercados eléctricos, destacando los beneficios de la participación en el mercado diario y en el de servicios auxiliares. Los resultados respaldan la adopción de los MPCs como una estrategia viable para modernizar las redes de distribución, acomodar la creciente integración de los DER y facilitar el logro de los objetivos de sostenibilidad en el ámbito energético.

Abstract

This master's thesis investigates the role of multiport power converters (MPCs) in enhancing the resilience and efficiency of distribution grids. The research focuses on reducing energy not supplied (ENS) and facilitating the integration of distributed energy resources (DER). Utilizing a modified IEEE 33-bus test system, simulations were conducted to evaluate the performance of MPCs under various scenarios, including single- and double-line failures and grid-forming and grid-following operation modes of distributed generation (DG) units.

Despite that in the base case the electrical performance of the distribution grid is already acceptable, the study reveals that MPCs significantly improve grid performance, particularly in voltage regulation and loss reduction. Economic feasibility analysis indicates that partial-scale MPCs provide a more cost-effective solution for grid performance enhancement. Additionally, the research assesses the potential revenue from battery energy storage systems (BESS) participation in electricity markets, highlighting the revenues from day-ahead markets and ancillary services markets. The findings support the adoption of MPCs as a viable strategy for modernizing distribution networks to accommodate increasing DER integration and achieve sustainable energy objectives.

Contents

RESUM	3
RESUMEN	4
ABSTRACT	5
ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS	9
LIST OF FIGURES	11
LIST OF TABLES	13
1. PREFACE	15
2. INTRODUCTION	17
2.1. Motivation	17
2.2. Scope	17
2.3. Objectives	18
3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND	19
3.1. Mathematical optimization	19
3.2. Power electronics for DER integration and grid stability enhancement	20
3.2.1. Comparison with switches	21
3.2.2. Multiport power converters	21
3.2.3. Voltage regulation	22
3.3. BESS and grid support markets	22
3.4. Electricity supply interruptions	27
4. METHODOLOGY	28
4.1. Tools and libraries	28
4.2. Case study	28
4.3. Code explanation	32
4.3.1. Energetic optimization	32
4.3.2. BESS participation in electricity markets	35
4.3.3. Grid-based optimization	37
4.4. Data representation	38
5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	40
5.1. Expected results	40
5.2. Single line failure	41
5.2.1. Without closing any switches or installing MPC	41

5.2.2.	Optimal MPC sizing.....	42
5.2.3.	Grid-following DG approach.....	44
5.3.	Double line failure.....	45
5.3.1.	Without closing any switches or installing MPC.....	45
5.3.2.	Optimal MPC sizing.....	46
5.3.3.	Grid-following approach.....	47
5.4.	Failure duration and MPC sizing.....	48
5.5.	BESS revenue in markets.....	50
5.6.	Electrical simulation.....	52
5.6.1.	Potential for voltage regulation.....	52
5.6.2.	Potential for loss reduction.....	54
5.6.3.	The impact of batteries.....	55
6.	ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT	56
7.	ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT	57
8.	SOCIAL AND GENDER EQUALITY ASSESSMENT	58
9.	CONCLUSIONS	59
10.	ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	61
11.	BIBLIOGRAPHY	62

Abbreviations and Symbols

List of abbreviations

AC	Alternating current
ADRS	Active demand response service
aFFR	Automatic frequency restoration reserve
BESS	Battery energy storage system
DC	Direct current
DER	Distributed energy resources
DG	Distributed generation
ENS	Energy not supplied
FCR	Frequency containment reserves
HV	High voltage
LP	Linear programming
LV	Low voltage
mFFR	Manual frequency restoration reserve
MIP	Mixed-integer programming
MPC	Multiport power converter
MV	Medium voltage
NLP	Nonlinear programming
OF	Objective function
OOP	Object oriented programming
OPF	Optimal power flow
PV	Photovoltaic
REE	Red Eléctrica de España
RES	Renewable energy sources
SD	Standard deviation
SOC	State of charge
SOP	Soft open point
VAT	Value-added tax
VRES	Variable renewable energy sources
VSC	Voltage Source Converters

List of symbols

A	Arbitrary coefficient ($A \geq 1$)
B	Arbitrary coefficient ($0 \leq B \leq 1$)
B_c	BESS cost [€/kWh]
B_{cycles}	Number of cycles [year^{-1}]
$CAPEX_{bat}$	Capital expenditure of the BESS [€]

C_{BESS}	Capacity of the BESS [kWh]
C_{bat}	Total BESS cost [€]
C_{conv-i}	Cost of terminal i of the converter [€/kW]
$C_{e,aFFR-down,t}$	Payment for energy delivered to aFFR downward at time t [€/kWh]
$C_{e,aFFR-up,t}$	Payment for energy delivered to aFFR upward at time t [€/kWh]
C_{ENS}	Cost of energy not supplied [€/kWh]
$C_{grid,t}$	Cost of the energy bought to the grid at time t [€/kWh]
C_{ENS}	Investment of the MPC [€]
$C_{p,aFFR-down,t}$	Capacity payment for participating in aFFR downward at time t [€/kW]
$C_{p,aFFR-up,t}$	Capacity payment for participating in aFFR upward at time t [€/kW]
E	Energy [kWh]
$E_{aFFR-down,t}$	Energy required by aFFR downward at time t [kWh/kW _{matched}]
$E_{aFFR-up,t}$	Energy required by aFFR upward at time t [kWh/kW _{matched}]
$E_{grid,t}$	Energy bought to the grid at time t [kWh]
h	Hours [h]
i_{kl}	Current at line kl [p.u.]
L_{prj}	Project lifetime [years]
$OPEX_{bat}$	Operating expenditure of the BESS [€]
P	Power [kW]
$P_{aFFR-down,t}$	Power matched in aFFR downward at time t [kW]
$P_{aFFR-up,t}$	Power matched in aFFR upward at time t [kW]
P_{BESS}	Power of the BESS [kW]
$P_{c,t}$	Charging power of the BESS at time t [kW]
$P_{d,t}$	Discharging power of the BESS at time t [kW]
$P_{DG,i,av}$	Power available of the distributed generation [kW]
$P_{DG-syst,i}$	Power of the distributed generation [kW]
$P_{load-syst,i}$	Power of the load [kW]
$P_{MPC,i}$	Power of MPC terminal i [kW]
r_{kl}	Resistance at line kl [p.u.]
S_b	Base power [kW]
$u_{GFL,i}$	Binary variable describing if a grid in system i is formed
$v_{i,t}$	Voltage at bus i at time t [p.u.]
η_{char}	Charging efficiency [dimensionless]
η_{disc}	Discharging efficiency [dimensionless]
τ	BESS self-discharge rate [h ⁻¹]

List of figures

Figure 1.1. Share of non-VRES sources in total electricity generation in selected synchronous areas, 2017-2026 [6].	16
Figure 3.1. Local and global minima in convex (left) and non-convex (right) functions	20
Figure 3.2. MPC schematic [5].	22
Figure 3.3. Day-ahead prices and energy traded in Spain during 03/06/2024 [19].	23
Figure 3.4. Schematic overview of the activation of operating reserves [21].	24
Figure 3.5. Tertiary regulation activation in Spain in 2023 [22].	25
Figure 3.6. Example of a project not beneficial for developers but beneficial for the system [24].	26
Figure 4.1. Schematic diagram of the IEEE 33 buses distribution network. Adapted from: [32].	29
Figure 4.2. Power generation and load over reference days.	29
Figure 4.3. Example of reconfiguration of buses. Adapted from: [5], [32].	34
Figure 4.4. Power limits for each of the ports [38].	37
Figure 4.5 Boxplot example. Own source.	38
Figure 4.6. Example of voltage data representation.	39
Figure 5.1. ENS for single faults at each of the lines.	42
Figure 5.2. ENS (top) and optimal MPC (bottom) power for 4-hour fault at the selected lines and MPC locations.	43
Figure 5.3. ENS for single faults at each of the lines in grid-following DG case.	44
Figure 5.4. ENS for each pair of faulted lines.	45
Figure 5.5. ENS (top) and optimal MPC power (bottom) for 4-hour fault at the selected lines and MPC locations.	46

Figure 5.6. ENS for single faults at each of the lines.....47

Figure 5.7. Unrestricted grid-following approach for fault at line 22 and MPC in position 35.
.....48

Figure 5.8. A and B coefficient restricted grid-following approach for 1-hour fault at line 22
and MPC in position 35.....49

Figure 5.9. P_{MPC} for A and B coefficient restricted grid-following approach for 1-hour fault.
.....49

Figure 5.10. Example of energy arbitrage for a 4-hour battery.....51

Figure 5.11. Voltage profiles for 300 kVA MPCs compared to normal operation profiles..53

Figure 5.12. Voltage profiles for 1000 kVA MPCs compared to normal operation profiles.
.....53

List of tables

Table 3.1. Cost of adjustment services in Spain in millions of euros [22].	25
Table 3.2. Breakdown of the final cost of electricity in Spain from 2020 to May 2024 [23].	26
Table 4.1. Reactive power compensators data [32].	30
Table 4.2. Generators data. Adapted from [32].	30
Table 4.3. Line data of the system [32].	31
Table 4.4. Bus data of the system [32].	32
Table 4.5. Grouping of the system's buses.	33
Table 4.6. BESS common parameters and capacities used.	36
Table 5.1. Key costs and project lifetime.	40
Table 5.2. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations.	43
Table 5.3. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations.	45
Table 5.4. Average ENS per common line fault.	46
Table 5.5. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations, double fault grid-forming DG.	47
Table 5.6. Average ENS per common line fault.	47
Table 5.7. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations, double fault grid-following DG.	47
Table 5.8. Comparison of grid-following approach between DG lost and DG available if the grid is formed.	50
Table 5.9. Economic analysis of BESS with and without aFFR participation.	51
Table 5.10. Mean voltage and SD for different MPC locations and power ratings.	54
Table 5.11. Impact of closing switches and MPC location and size on power line losses.	55

Table 6.1. Budget for the development of the thesis.	56
Table 7.1. Specific emission factors for the Spanish electrical mix from 2019 to June 2024 [40].	57
Table 7.2. Total CO ₂ emissions resulting from the development of this thesis.	57

1. Preface

The effects of global warming caused by human activity are already noticeable today, with increasingly frequent extreme weather events and a rise in the average global temperature. In the Paris Agreement, 175 countries committed to keeping this rise "well below 2°C" compared to pre-industrial levels to avoid damaging the planet's health [1].

Combating climate change is an uneven process around the world. While most developed countries incentivize decarbonization, developing countries like India and China have not yet peaked in emissions and seek energy sources to match their economic growth and ensure energy security. This diversity is evident with 175 GW of coal power plants under construction in early 2022 and 150 GW of installed photovoltaic capacity in 2021. At the same time, 754 million people, mainly in Sub-Saharan Africa, lack access to electricity [2].

Nevertheless, it is evident that there is progress toward decarbonizing the energy sector globally. In advanced economies, electricity demand growth is being supported by the ongoing electrification of the residential and transport sectors, as well as a notable expansion of the data center sector. In 2023, renewable capacity increased by a record 473 GW, representing a remarkable 61% increase compared to 293 GW in 2022 and 86% of the total added capacity in 2023, with solar energy (346 GW) and wind energy (116 GW) being the most notable [3]. Beyond the political will to reduce emissions, the expansion of these technologies has been driven by cost reductions, making them economically attractive options. Since 2010, solar photovoltaic has seen the largest cost reduction, with the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for new large-scale projects decreasing from 445 \$/MWh in 2010 to 49 \$/MWh in 2022 [4].

The penetration of variable renewable energy sources (VRES) in the electricity mix is rapidly increasing, Figure 1.1. These sources can not only experiment fast oscillations in their power output but are also power electronics based, in contrast with traditional power plants based on synchronous generators. This shift poses a threat to grid stability as it introduces more variability and reduces the overall system's inertia.

Ensuring power quality is becoming increasingly complex, and a lot of effort is already underway to address this challenge. The European Union is investing in research projects in this field under Horizon Europe programs such as iPLUG with grant agreement 101069770 [5], in the framework of which this project has been developed. Furthermore, these VRES are being integrated as large-scale power plants but also as distributed generators (DG) at medium and low voltage. This compromises voltage regulation since the lower the voltage the more relevant the role of active power in its regulation. Combined with the increasing demand, using tap-changing transformers might not be

enough to control voltage levels, leading to possible generation or load curtailment. Similarly, this additional stress can lead to exceeding line capacities or unacceptable line losses, requiring new solutions to modernise distribution networks.

The integration of VRES requires advanced grid management techniques, including the use of energy storage systems, demand response strategies, and sophisticated grid control algorithms. Power electronics play a crucial role in addressing this problem too, not only in the power generation side but also in providing grid services. In this context, multiport power converters (MPCs) present potential to improve the efficiency and power density of applications that require several power conversion stages.

Figure 1.1. Share of non-VRES sources in total electricity generation in selected synchronous areas, 2017-2026 [6].

2. Introduction

This document delves into the potential of MPCs in enhancing the stability and efficiency of distribution grids, focusing on the capacity to reduce the supply shortage in case of faults in the system. By integrating distributed energy resources (DER), MPCs offer a robust solution for modern power systems facing increasing demand and renewable energy integration. The analysis is grounded in a comprehensive case study involving the enhanced IEEE 33-bus system, with minor modifications to better represent a modern grid. Through detailed simulations, the aim is to showcase how MPCs can improve grid reliability, manage power flows, and support voltage regulation. Additionally, the document highlights the economic feasibility of MPCs in some of their different possible configurations, as well as that of battery energy storage systems (BESS) in wholesale electricity markets, which can be integrated into the grid via MPC too.

2.1. Motivation

This work originates from the need to adapt the existing grid, that was planned for a centralised power generation and unidirectional power flow, to the new paradigm that includes the massive integration of DER into the grid, such as photovoltaic (PV) and wind generation, BESS, electrification of the demand and active consumer participation. This causes the distribution network to face significant challenges in maintaining stability and service quality.

Integrating DER effectively can address several key issues such as environmental sustainability, energy efficiency, and economic benefits at both macro and local levels. Furthermore, enhancing grid resilience and improving the efficiency of energy distribution are critical goals that align with broader societal needs, including the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the advancement of sustainable development objectives. This thesis delves into how MPCs can facilitate the integration of DER into the distribution grid, reduce ENS, and improve grid performance.

2.2. Scope

The scope of this master's thesis encompasses a comprehensive analysis of the role of MPCs in enhancing the stability and efficiency of distribution grids. The study involves a literature review, the modification and simulation of a modified IEEE 33-bus distribution system, and an evaluation of the economic feasibility of MPCs, focusing on their ability to reduce energy not supplied (ENS) and integrate DER.

Multiple possible configurations of MPCs can be supposed. Although, due to workload, only some have been considered. Integrating distributed generation (DG) units through the converter, electric vehicle, connection of loads directly to the converter, interfacing more than two ports with the alternating current (AC) grid, and integrating the grid at different voltage levels are some of the configuration options that MPC offer but remain out of the scope of this work. The computational power has limited the scope of the simulations. To complete them in a reasonable time, simulations involving the IEEE 33 bus case study were performed for reference days with the aim of a compromise between accurate and fast optimizations.

Regarding the BESS participation in markets, the work does not present strategies to optimize it, rather, it presents the theoretical maximum obtainable revenue from this activity in the supposed scenario.

In all the cases, the work is limited to theoretical data and simulations, without having tested them in the real distribution network.

2.3. Objectives

The main objective of this master's thesis is to analyse how Multiport Power Converters can enhance the resilience and efficiency of the distribution grid while reducing the energy not supplied and facilitating the integration of DER. This goal aims to address the challenges posed by the increasing integration of distributed energy resources and the loss of synchronous generators.

The specific objectives are:

- Conduct a review of existing research on MPCs and other power electronics-based equipment and their integration into distribution grids.
- Develop a modified IEEE 33-bus test system with increased renewable energy generation. Define scenarios for single- and double-line failures to assess the impact of MPC on energy supply analysing both grid-forming and grid-following operation modes for DG units.
- Compare MPCs and switches in the context of energy-based simulation and grid-based simulation.
- Analyse the cost-benefit of installing MPCs at partial-scale and full-scale for ENS reduction and grid performance enhancement.
- In the context of taking advantage of the capability of MPC to integrate several conversion stages and technologies, develop guiding simulation to assess the feasibility of BESS participation in wholesale electricity markets, both for energy arbitrage and ancillary services.

3. Theoretical background

This chapter provides the foundational concepts and theories that support the analyses and methodologies used in this work. It covers mathematical optimization, the role of power electronics in DER integration and grid stability enhancement focusing on MPC. Moreover, it examines the economic and technical incentives for BESS participation in electricity markets, focusing on energy arbitrage and grid support markets. Finally, the economic and social impact of electricity shortages are presented, as well as the causes for them. This theoretical background sets the stage for understanding the subsequent analyses and results presented in this thesis.

3.1. Mathematical optimization

From the Mathematical Optimization Society [7], “*in a mathematical optimization (or programming) problem, one seeks to minimize or maximize a real function of real or integer variables, subject to constraints on the variables*”. It focuses on the mathematical properties of these problems, developing and implementing algorithms to solve them, and applying these algorithms to real-world issues. The general form of a mathematical optimization problem is the following:

$$\min_{x \in R^n} f(x) \quad \text{Eq. 3.1}$$

subject to:

$$h_i(x) = 0; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad \text{Eq. 3.2}$$

$$g_j(x) \leq 0; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r \quad \text{Eq. 3.3}$$

where $x \in R^n$ are the decision variables, $f(x)$ the objective function to minimize or maximize, Eq. 3.2 the m equality constraints and Eq. 3.3 the r inequality constraints [8].

The properties of the constraints significantly influence the complexity and methods used to solve the optimization problem. Real-number decision variables can often be addressed with techniques from calculus and linear algebra. Integer variables introduce combinatorial complexity, requiring discrete optimization methods. Linear constraints lead to linear programming (LP) problems, solvable with methods like the simplex method, while nonlinear constraints lead to nonlinear programming (NLP), requiring advanced techniques such as gradient methods or heuristic algorithms.

In optimization problems, solutions can be categorized as local or global. A local solution is a point where the objective function value is lower than that of any nearby feasible points. In contrast, a global solution has the lowest objective function value among all feasible points. In convex programming, local and global solutions coincide. However, nonlinear

problems often have local solutions that are not global. It is important to consider that many algorithms are designed to find local solutions due to the complexity of identifying global solutions [9].

Figure 3.1. Local and global minima in convex (left) and non-convex (right) functions [10]

Various solvers are used to tackle optimization problems efficiently by utilizing advanced algorithms and computational techniques. These solvers, including Gurobi, CPLEX, IPOPT, and others, are designed to handle different types of optimization problems such as linear, integer, and nonlinear programming. They provide robust solutions by implementing state-of-the-art algorithms, enabling the efficient handling of large-scale and complex problems across numerous applications in industry and research. The use of these solvers facilitates the practical implementation of optimization techniques, but careful consideration must be given to the choice of solver, as each is specifically effective for certain types of problems.

3.2. Power electronics for DER integration and grid stability enhancement

In the context of modern power systems, integrating DER and enhancing grid stability is crucial, and power electronics play a significant role in addressing these challenges. Among these technologies, various advanced power electronics devices and systems are noteworthy for their ability to interconnect multiple power sources and loads, offering versatile solutions for power conversion and distribution.

Voltage source converters are self-commutated converters that use devices suitable for high power electronic applications, such as insulated-gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) [11]. VSCs have several advantageous features: they can operate in grid-forming mode, provide good power quality thanks to their high commutation frequencies, provide grid services, and offer bidirectional power flow by inverting the current direction for power reversal. Additionally, VSCs are scalable, making them suitable for a wide range of applications. These applications range from connecting low-power batteries or

photovoltaic (PV) systems to the grid to high-voltage direct current (HVDC) systems in the gigawatt (GW) range.

Soft Open Points (SOPs), a similar and more mature equipment compared to MPCs, are designed for improving the performance distribution networks. Utilizing VSCs, SOPs manage both active and reactive power flows. By connecting adjacent feeders, they inject or absorb active power, stabilizing voltage levels during peak loads or faults. SOPs also provide reactive power compensation, essential for voltage profile management.

Their dynamic control capabilities allow real-time adjustments to network conditions, beneficial for handling the variable nature of renewable energy. This ensures rapid responses to power generation fluctuations, maintaining voltage stability [12]. By balancing loads and managing power flows, SOPs smooth voltage profiles, preventing disruptions that could affect sensitive electronics and industrial processes.

3.2.1. Comparison with switches

Both switches and power electronics-based devices are employed to enhance the efficiency and reliability of power delivery but present substantial differences in terms of cost and capabilities. Switches are traditional electromechanical devices used to control the flow of electricity within the grid. They are relatively inexpensive and are primarily used to reconfigure the network and isolate faults. Switches are present in distribution networks, which despite being meshed are typically operated in a radial configuration with the switches open. That's because a radial network is less complex to operate and can use simpler protection equipment. Despite their low cost, switches do not offer the controllability that advanced power electronics do and are limited to a binary operation.

In the search for cost-effectiveness, some authors have proposed combining them. For example, one approach involves using a hybrid system with a partial-scale back-to-back SOP and a parallel load switch [13]. In this configuration, under normal operation the small converter regulates power flow and voltage under normal conditions while the parallel, normally open switchable line enables complete power recovery during faults, which otherwise would be limited to the SOP capacity.

Another proposed solution, applicable for multiterminal converters, is to design each terminal to have different powers, connected to a multiterminal switch to reconfigure them. Compared to hard-wire ones, this method significantly increases the flexibility and performance of the network with a significant cost reduction [14], [15].

3.2.2. Multiport power converters

Multiport power converters are devices based on VSC designed to manage and control

the exchange of power between more than two ports. They are typically developed to enhance the efficiency and power density of applications involving several conversion stages [5].

Figure 3.2. MPC schematic [5].

These converters are broadly classified based on their power conversion stages and the methods used for power transfer between connected devices. The classifications are divided into single-stage and hybrid multistage converters, each with isolated and non-isolated variants. Single-stage MPCs are divided into isolated and non-isolated types. Isolated MPCs utilize a power transformer to provide galvanic isolation, using high-frequency modulation techniques to manage power transfer. Non-isolated MPCs, on the other hand, maintain a direct physical connection between all ports, eliminating the need for a transformer. The third group of MPCs involves hybrid multistage converters, which incorporate two or more power conversion stages, typically combining both isolated and non-isolated sections.

3.2.3. Voltage regulation

Currently, voltage in distribution systems (which use AC) is mainly regulated by on-load-tap-change transformers, shunt capacitors and circuit breakers [16]. Voltage regulation is influenced by the nature of power and the X/R ratio at different voltage levels. At high voltages (HV), where the X/R ratio is high, voltage regulation is primarily related to reactive power. In contrast, at low voltages (LV), where the X/R ratio is low, voltage regulation is more affected by active power. However, at medium voltages (MV), where both reactance (X) and resistance (R) are significant, and the X/R ratio is medium, effective voltage regulation requires consideration of both active and reactive power [17]. In MV and LV, when all traditional voltage regulation has been exhausted, generation curtailment can be necessary to limit overvoltages and load curtailment to limit undervoltages [18].

3.3. BESS and grid support markets

Multiport power converters offer a solution for integrating battery energy storage systems into the grid. To fully present the economic and technical potential of MPCs with BESS,

the participation of BESS in the electricity markets should be studied. These technologies can participate through traditional energy arbitrage and grid support markets.

Energy arbitrage essentially comprises storing electricity at times when energy is plentiful and inexpensive, and discharging it to the grid when it is scarce and most expensive. Typically, BESS performs one full charge and discharge cycle per day to maximize profits while limiting degradation. This activity is becoming increasingly profitable with the massive introduction of VRES in the mix, which offer their energy at low or even negative prices but cannot control their generation. Price variations of 50€/MWh or more in a single day are quite common in European electricity markets, Figure 3.3 illustrates this for a day heavily influenced by PV generation in Spain.

Figure 3.3. Day-ahead prices and energy traded in Spain during 03/06/2024 [19].

In AC systems, monitoring the frequency value is possible to determine the equilibrium between generation and consumption. Frequency drops when there's more consumption than demand and increases in the opposite case. Frequency restoration markets play a crucial role in maintaining the stability and efficiency of power systems, especially in grids with high penetration of renewable energy.

In Spain, primary regulation is a mandatory, non-remunerated service provided by generators [20]. Its main function is to automatically correct instantaneous imbalances between production and consumption. This is achieved by immediate and autonomous adjustments in generator output through turbine speed regulators. This service is equivalent to the European Frequency Containment Reserves (FCR).

Secondary regulation is an optional service that is compensated through market mechanisms. It aims to maintain the balance between generation and demand by correcting deviations from the scheduled exchanges and frequency. This service operates

within a time frame of 20 seconds to 15 minutes. The compensation is based on two factors: availability (power) and utilization (energy). The energy will generally be valued at the marginal price of the tertiary regulation energy that would have been needed to replace the performed secondary regulation energy in that period. This regulation corresponds to the European automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves (aFRR) [20].

Tertiary regulation is also an optional service but with a mandatory offer requirement for qualified units. It is managed and compensated through market mechanisms. The goal of this service is to resolve imbalances between generation and consumption and to restore the secondary regulation reserves. This is done by adjusting the operating schedules of the production and pumping consumption units. The tertiary regulation reserves are defined as the maximum power variation a production unit can achieve within 15 minutes, and this power must be maintainable for at least two hours. This service is equivalent to the European manual Frequency Restoration Reserves (mFRR) [20].

Figure 3.4. Schematic overview of the activation of operating reserves [21].

In recent years, regulatory changes in Spain have been implemented to increase the flexibility and participation of demand and storage facilities in balancing services, specifically in the Replacement Reserve (RR), aFRR, and mFRR. These changes are aimed at adapting Spanish Operating Procedures to accommodate demand facilities and storage in balancing markets, aligning with the approved Spanish Terms and Conditions.

The adaptation of these procedures, which entered into force on January 26th, 2021, followed a public consultation period between March and April 2020. Key regulatory changes include allowing individual or aggregated participation of demand and storage

facilities, reducing the minimum bid capacity for qualification tests from 10 MW to 1 MW, and increasing flexibility in prequalification processes to facilitate the inclusion of new items in pre-existing balancing service provider units through aggregated participation.

Despite BESS paper in these markets is not relevant yet, another storage technology is a major player. Pumped-hydro facilities are currently crucial participants in these markets, engaging in both upward and downward balancing:

- When pumping: They can participate in the upward market by reducing consumption and in the downward market by increasing consumption.
- When generating: They can participate in the upward market by increasing generation and in the downward market by decreasing it.

Considering the cost reductions expected for BESS and the possibility to be aggregated, they show potential for participating in these markets. Probably, due to their higher power-to-energy ratio, they seem more suited to the aFFR than the mRFF.

Figure 3.5. Tertiary regulation activation in Spain in 2023 [22].

These markets are also increasingly important with higher penetration of VRES, Table 3.1, Table 3.2. In fact, adjustment services represented a higher part of the final energy price than SPOT market price in April 2024 (18.02 €/MWh with respect to 14.26 €/MWh).

Table 3.1. Cost of adjustment services in Spain in millions of euros [22].

	2020	2021	2022	2023
Technical restrictions	501.46	724.58	1103.94	1896.33
Frequency reserve and ADRS ¹	94.62	261.72	577.91	607.56
Other	4.73	41.20	47.18	-1.57
Total	600.81	1027.50	1729.03	2502.31
YoY increment	-	71.02 %	68.28 %	44.72 %

¹ Active Demand Response Service.

Table 3.2. Breakdown of the final cost of electricity in Spain from 2020 to May 2024 [23].

	2020	2021	2022	2023	Jan/24	Feb/24	Mar/24	Apr/24	May/24
Daily market	35.21	113.17	170.41	88.92	76.88	40.80	21.56	14.26	30.56
Intraday market	-0.02	-0.02	-0.20	-0.10	-0.09	-0.09	-0.05	-0.13	0.02
Technical restrictions PDBF	1.79	1.83	2.00	3.93	2.98	4.05	7.27	9.69	9.22
Secondary regulating band	0.40	1.07	2.36	2.33	1.94	1.81	1.77	1.61	1.99
Real-time technical constraints	0.33	1.16	2.68	3.63	3.10	3.21	3.47	5.69	3.18
Non-compliance with energy balance	-0.02	-0.07	-0.28	-0.21	-0.14	-0.08	-0.02	-0.02	-0.06
Cost of deviations	0.17	0.47	0.84	0.51	0.49	0.36	0.31	0.54	0.47
Balance deviations	-0.07	-0.18	-0.25	0.02	0.31	0.26	0.45	0.60	0.25
Power factor control	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.08	-0.09	-0.14	-0.13	-0.12	-
Balance PO 14.6	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.06
Adjustment Services	2.54	4.23	7.33	10.17	8.61	9.51	13.15	18.02	15.11
Capacity payments	2.63	1.31	0.33	0.24	0.35	0.33	0.19	0.15	0.15
RD-L 10/2022 Mechanism	0.00	0.00	26.47	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total price (€/MWh)	40.38	118.69	204.34	99.43	85.75	50.55	34.85	32.30	45.84
Closing energy (TWh)	236.54	242.36	235.88	230.89	20.96	19.05	19.08	17.89	17.99

While BESS offer significant system-wide benefits, these are not always directly monetizable for project owners. Savings on transmission and distribution systems and reductions in market costs by displacing expensive technologies are system benefits that do not generate direct revenue for developers. This disparity can slow the growth of BESS projects due to insufficient economic incentives for developers despite overall positive system impacts, Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6. Example of a project not beneficial for developers but beneficial for the system [24].

3.4. Electricity supply interruptions

Electricity supply interruptions have significant economic impacts, which have been widely analysed in the literature [25], [26] affecting various sectors differently and influencing the overall economy. Costs also fluctuate daily, peaking during high economic activity hours, and vary geographically, with regions reliant on electricity-intensive processes facing higher costs. Additionally, disruption in the power supply can cause cascading effects throughout the economy, amplifying the overall impact. The time duration of the fault also affects the cost, which in Scotland cost ranges from approximately 4.3 £/kWh for a one-minute interruption to about 8.1 £/kWh for interruptions lasting three hours or more [25]. In Spain, the cost of one kWh of electricity not supplied is around 6 €/kWh [26].

The most economically affected sectors in the event of a power interruption are those with high interdependencies on electricity and offer a higher-value added, including telecommunications and financial services. Conversely, high energy-intensive sectors with low value-added, such as agriculture and metal sectors, show lower ENS costs. Households, while not as severely affected in terms of direct economic loss as industrial sectors, face considerable inconvenience and disruption of daily activities, contributing significantly to the overall societal cost of energy not supplied.

Failures in the system can be caused by several causes, unpredictable and predictable that can be prevented like flashover in the insulators due to pollution. Overhead lines contribute to about 50% of the network outages, leaving the remainder to be distributed between cable lines, transformers, and other devices. This is primarily due to their exposure to environmental factors like lightning, wildfires, and wind [27], [28].

Cables also face significant challenges, with faults often resulting from insulation degradation, thermal overloading, and mechanical damage. Transformers frequently fail due to aging, thermal stress, and electrical disturbances. Monitoring techniques such as thermal imaging and electrical impedance spectroscopy are essential for predicting and preventing transformer failures, ensuring timely maintenance, and reducing unexpected outages [28]. By focusing on the main sources of faults—overhead lines, transformers, and cables—utilities can implement targeted measures to mitigate the impact of these faults and ensure a continuous and reliable power supply.

4. Methodology

This section details the methodological approach employed in this study, focusing on the tools, techniques, and processes used to achieve the research objectives. The methodology outlines the case study framework, code implementation, and data representation strategies adopted for the analysis of the integration of MPCs in the distribution grid. It presents the methodologies used for obtaining the results in Chapter 5, including energy-based optimization, grid-based optimization, and BESS participation in markets, which also follows an energetic approach.

4.1. Tools and libraries

This work utilizes Pyomo, an open-source optimization modelling language for Python, to implement and solve optimization problems. Pyomo provides a flexible and extensible environment for modelling linear, nonlinear, and mixed-integer optimization problems [29]. Its integration with Python allows for leveraging powerful data handling and computational capabilities, making it a suitable choice for the complex optimization tasks required in this study. For solving the energetic optimization problems, the IPOPT [30] solver is used while HiGHS [31] is used for the grid-based simulations. Both are state-of-the-art solvers for large-scale problems, providing robust and efficient solutions.

Additionally, the object-oriented programming (OOP) paradigm is employed to structure the code. OOP facilitates modularity, code reuse, and clarity, making the implementation of complex systems more manageable. By encapsulating data and functions within objects, the codebase remains organized and scalable, which is crucial for handling the various components of the energy and grid optimization models.

The optimization was performed on a system running Microsoft Windows 11 Home, equipped with an Intel Core i7-8750H CPU @ up to 4.1 GHz and 8 GB of RAM. The hardware and software configuration provided sufficient computational power to execute the optimization, although some simulations span well above 5 minutes. This computational demand underlines the decision to run simulations over selected reference days instead of an entire year, balancing accuracy with practical feasibility.

4.2. Case study

The case study is based on the enhanced IEEE 33-bus system [32], a well-established benchmark for distribution network analysis. For the purposes of this study, some minor

modifications have been made to the original IEEE 33-bus configuration to better align with the specific objectives of this research.

The most significant modification is the increase in the installed capacity of renewable energy sources, from the original 0.8 MW to 2.1 MW. This adjustment is essential to study the impact of higher penetration of renewable energy sources on the grid's stability and performance, note that even after the adjustment the VRES generation is still significantly lower than the demand, Figure 4.2. Another considerable modification is the reduction of the minimum voltage from 0.95 p.u. to 0.90 p.u., this permits the obtention a feasible solution for the optimal power flow (OPF) when no actions are done. Anyhow, one of the aims of the electrical simulation part is to demonstrate how the use of a MPC permits voltage regulation, not only to the original 0.95-1.05 range but as close to 1 as possible.

Figure 4.1. Schematic diagram of the IEEE 33 buses distribution network. Adapted from: [32].

Figure 4.2. Power generation and load over reference days.

Figure 4.2 illustrates the power generation and load over four reference days within the modified IEEE 33-bus system. The graph shows the variation in power output from

photovoltaic (PV) units located at buses 22 and 33, and wind turbines at buses 18 and 25. Additionally, the total renewable generation and the load demand are depicted.

Over the four days, the PV and wind generation exhibit significant variability, reflecting typical renewable energy patterns influenced by weather conditions and time of day. The load curve also varies, showing peaks and troughs corresponding to the daily demand cycles. It is important to note that the four days are not consecutive days. The profile of the first day can be attributed to winter, with high demand and very low PV generation. The second day represents spring, characterized by low demand. The third day corresponds to summer, with high PV generation and high demand during the central hours of the day due to cooling needs. The fourth day represents autumn or winter.

Overall, these four reference days aim to provide an accurate approximation of running the simulation throughout 365 days but with much less computational effort. This approach ensures that various seasonal and demand patterns are captured, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the system's performance.

The following tables provide a comprehensive overview of the network data for the modified IEEE 33-bus system. These tables detail the essential parameters and configurations used in the simulation study. Table 4.1 describes the parameters of the reactive power compensators and Table 4.2 the generators. Table 4.3 presents the line data, specifying the impedance, line charging, and thermal limits for each line segment. Finally, Table lists the bus data, including the voltage information, active and reactive power demand and bus type, where the slack is the reference bus, and a PG bus is a bus with only demand and a PV with only generation.

Table 4.1. Reactive power compensators data [32].

Bus number	Type	Reactive capacity [kVAR]
18	Capacitive	400
33	Capacitive	600

Table 4.2. Generators data. Adapted from [32].

Bus number	Type	Active capacity [kW]	Reactive capacity [kVAR]
1	Feeder	4000	400
18	Wind	429	0
22	PV	286	0
25	Wind	716	0
33	PV	684	0

Table 4.3. Line data of the system [32].

Line number	From bus	To bus	R [Ω]	X [Ω]	Type
1	1	2	0.09	0.05	Fixed
2	2	3	0.49	0.25	Fixed
3	3	4	0.37	0.19	Fixed
4	4	5	0.38	0.19	Fixed
5	5	6	0.82	0.71	Fixed
6	6	7	0.19	0.62	Fixed
7	7	8	0.71	0.24	Fixed
8	8	9	1.03	0.74	Fixed
9	9	10	1.04	0.74	Fixed
10	10	11	0.20	0.07	Fixed
11	11	12	0.37	0.12	Fixed
12	12	13	1.47	1.16	Fixed
13	13	14	0.54	0.71	Fixed
14	14	15	0.59	0.53	Fixed
15	15	16	0.75	0.55	Fixed
16	16	17	1.29	1.72	Fixed
17	17	18	0.73	0.57	Fixed
18	2	19	0.16	0.16	Fixed
19	19	20	1.50	1.36	Fixed
20	20	21	0.41	0.48	Fixed
21	21	22	0.71	0.94	Fixed
22	3	23	0.45	0.31	Fixed
23	23	24	0.90	0.71	Fixed
24	24	25	0.90	0.70	Fixed
25	6	26	0.20	0.10	Fixed
26	26	27	0.28	0.14	Fixed
27	27	28	1.06	0.93	Fixed
28	28	29	0.80	0.70	Fixed
29	29	30	0.51	0.26	Fixed
30	30	31	0.97	0.96	Fixed
31	31	32	0.31	0.36	Fixed
32	32	33	0.34	0.53	Fixed
33	8	21	2.00	2.00	Switchable
34	12	22	2.00	2.00	Switchable
35	25	29	0.50	0.50	Switchable
36	18	33	2.00	2.00	Switchable

Table 4.4. Bus data of the system [32].

Bus number	Type	Active demand [kW]	Reactive demand [kVAR]	V_n [kV]	V_{min} [p.u.]	V_{max} [p.u.]
1	Slack	99.41	59.65	12.66	0.90	1.05
2	PQ	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
3	PQ	119.29	79.53	12.66	0.90	1.05
4	PQ	59.65	29.82	12.66	0.90	1.05
5	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
6	PQ	198.82	99.41	12.66	0.90	1.05
7	PQ	198.82	99.41	12.66	0.90	1.05
8	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
9	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
10	PQ	44.73	29.82	12.66	0.90	1.05
11	PQ	59.65	34.79	12.66	0.90	1.05
12	PQ	59.65	34.79	12.66	0.90	1.05
13	PQ	119.29	79.53	12.66	0.90	1.05
14	PQ	59.65	9.94	12.66	0.90	1.05
15	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
16	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
17	PQ	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
18	PQ/PV	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
19	PQ	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
20	PQ	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
21	PQ	89.47	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
22	PQ/PV	89.47	49.70	12.66	0.90	1.05
23	PQ	417.52	198.82	12.66	0.90	1.05
24	PQ	417.52	198.82	12.66	0.90	1.05
25	PQ/PV	59.65	24.85	12.66	0.90	1.05
26	PQ	59.65	24.85	12.66	0.90	1.05
27	PQ	59.65	19.88	12.66	0.90	1.05
28	PQ	119.29	69.59	12.66	0.90	1.05
29	PQ	198.82	594.51	12.66	0.90	1.05
30	PQ	149.11	69.59	12.66	0.90	1.05
31	PQ	208.76	99.41	12.66	0.90	1.05
32	PQ	59.65	39.76	12.66	0.90	1.05
33	PV	0.00	0.00	12.66	0.90	1.05

4.3. Code explanation

4.3.1. Energetic optimization

The objective function (OF) of the energetic simulation system is designed to minimize the

total costs associated with the energy system over the project's lifespan. It encompasses various cost components, each representing a different aspect of the system's operational and capital expenses. It should be noted that some of the terms are being multiplied by the project lifespan (L_{prj}), these are the annual terms, including the cost of the energy bought to the grid (C_{grid}), the operating expense (OPEX) of the battery ($OPEX_{bat}$) and the cost of the energy not supplied (C_{ENS}).

On the other hand, the investments that span the entire lifespan of the project are the cost of the MPC itself (C_{MPC}) and the capital expense (CAPEX) of the battery ($CAPEX_{bat}$). The BESS is understood as a single-time investment despite the 30 years of project lifespan due to being only used to deliver energy in case of faults, leading to minimal annual cycles. The objective function of the mathematical optimization problem is defined in Eq. 4.1:

$$OF = \min[L_{prj} \cdot (C_{grid} + OPEX_{bat} + C_{ENS}) + C_{MPC} + CAPEX_{bat}] \quad \text{Eq. 4.1}$$

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_i C_{conv-i} \cdot P_{MPC-i} \quad \text{Eq. 4.2}$$

Due to the energetic nature of the simulation, it is possible to group all the elements that are physically connected by lines in a single node, neglecting aspects such as voltages, line losses, or reactive power. These nodes will be called systems. With the information of the faulted line(s), the code uses a dictionary to group the different buses as defined in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5. Grouping of the system's buses.

System 1	Buses connected to the main grid
System 2	Buses that can be connected to the main grid via MPC
System 3	Buses that can be connected to the MPC but not to the main grid via MPC
System 4	Isolated buses
System 5	Battery energy storage system

To avoid energy exchange system 4, the cost of the power electronics connected to system 4 is several orders of magnitude higher to represent its isolation with respect to the MPC. For example, consider a scenario where there are faults in lines 22 and 25, and an MPC is located at position 36, refer to Figure 4.3. In this case:

- **System 1** comprises buses 1-22.
- **System 2** includes buses 26-33.
- **System 3** is empty.
- **System 4** contains buses 23-25.
- **System 5** consists of the BESS.

Figure 4.3. Example of reconfiguration of buses. Adapted from: [5], [32].

A single MPC cannot simultaneously have buses in both system 2 and system 3. If there are buses in system 2, system 3 must be empty, and vice versa. This is because having a non-empty system 1, which includes buses connected directly to the main grid, allows buses in system 2 (which can connect to the main grid via the MPC). However, for the existence of buses in system 3 the MPC cannot have access to the grid, Table 4.5.

The constraint introduced to the code is that the converter's power inflow must be equal to its power outflow Eq. 4.3, in a converter lossless supposition. In practice, since importing energy from the grid is much cheaper than installing a battery, $P_{MPC,5}$ will be zero in case the MPC has access to the grid, Eq. 4.4. If that's not the case, the only option will be to import the energy from the BESS, Eq. 4.5.

$$\sum_{\forall k} P_{MPC-i,t} = 0 \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.3}$$

$$P_{MPC,2,t} = -P_{MPC,1,t} \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.4}$$

$$P_{MPC,3,t} = -P_{MPC,5,t} \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.5}$$

4.3.1.1. Grid-following approach

For the grid-following approach of the energetic simulation, the objective is to consider the generation of DG units only if they find themselves in a relatively strong grid. Obviously, this will be always the case for units in system 1 and never for those in system 4. Thus, the main challenge is to properly consider this operation mode for those in systems 2 and 3. For that, the implementation supports two options that can be used together or separately. The first one, Eq. 4.7 is to consider their generation plus the power apported by the converter to be an arbitrary number of times $A \geq 1$ higher than the consumption of the isolated buses. The second option, Eq. 4.8, is to consider that the power of the converter needs to be higher than a specific coefficient ($0 \leq B \leq 1$) of the load:

$$P_{DG-syst,i,t} \leq P_{DG,i,av,t} \cdot u_{GFL,i,t} \quad i = 2,3, \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.6}$$

$$P_{DG-syst,i,t} + P_{MPC,i,t} \geq P_{load-syst,i,t} \cdot u_{GFL,i,t} \cdot A \quad i = 2,3, \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.7}$$

$$P_{MPC-syst,i,t} \geq P_{load-syst,i,t} \cdot u_{GFL,i,t} \cdot B \quad i = 2,3, \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.8}$$

$$u_{GFL,i,t} \in \{0, 1\} \quad i = 2,3, \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.9}$$

Where $P_{DG-syst,i,t}$ is the power generation of the DG in system i , $P_{DG,i,av,t}$ the power available and $u_{GFL,i,t}$ a binary variable that gets the value 0 if the grid isn't formed and 1 otherwise.

4.3.2. BESS participation in electricity markets

This chapter analyses the other potential revenues of the BESS, in a case study similar to that of the previous sections. Since the generation from the DERs is much lower than the load demand for all time periods, Figure 4.2, the only option for exploiting economically is by participating in electricity markets: day-ahead markets and support service markets.

For the day-ahead energy prices the data from the Iberian market operator (OMIE [19]) has been used. On the other hand, data regarding ancillary markets is published by Spanish transmission system operator, Red Eléctrica de España (REE) [23]. In both cases, data from 2023 has been used.

Regarding the secondary response data, REE publishes both the capacity data (the one service providers receive for being available in €/MW) and the actual energy participants are requested MWh and €/MWh. However, the benefits from ancillary services should be regarded as upper bounds and are likely to be lower. The primary challenge addressed by ancillary services is uncertainty. When a bid is matched, the provider receives availability (power) revenue but does not know if it will be required to deliver energy. Despite this, the analysis considers the energy requested throughout 2023 as an input for evaluating the benefits.

It is worth mentioning that there are also limitations regarding the minimum power of bids in ancillary services. In Spain, the minimum bid size is 1 MW [33], whereas other markets, such as Finland, allow lower values, like 0.1 MW [34]. For the optimization, no minimum bid value has been considered. The justification for this is the possibility of participating through aggregation. Aggregation enables smaller distributed energy resources (DERs) to combine their capacities to meet the minimum bid requirements, thereby facilitating their involvement in the markets.

$$OF = \min \left[R + 70 \cdot B_{cycles} + 0.02 \cdot \sum_{\forall t} (P_{aFFR-up,t} + P_{aFFR-down,t}) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4.10}$$

$$R = \sum_{\forall t} E_{grid,t} \cdot C_{grid,t} - P_{aFFR-up,t} \cdot C_{p,aFFR-up,t} - P_{aFFR-up,t} \cdot E_{aFFR-up,t} \cdot C_{e,aFFR-up,t} - P_{aFFR-down,t} \cdot C_{p,aFFR-down,t} - P_{aFFR-down,t} \cdot E_{aFFR-down,t} \cdot C_{e,aFFR-down,t} \quad \text{Eq. 4.11}$$

Essentially, by minimizing the objective function the aim is to maximize revenues from aFFR and minimize cycles, up to a certain point, and energy bought to the grid. The latter is done by energy arbitrage and represented by the total cost of the energy bought to the grid $E_{grid,t} \cdot C_{grid,t}$, since it is considered that the BESS is installed in a system with a much higher load than its capacity, and BESS will be used to store cheap energy and avoid buyer more expensive one.

In the R coefficient definition, the second term refers to the availability (power) payment in aFFR upward and the third refers to the energy delivered payment where $P_{aFFR-up,t}$ is the matched power and $E_{aFFR-up,t}$ the requested energy that has to be delivered [kWh/kW_{matched}]. Finally, the last term of the objective function is used to avoid participating in upward and downward markets in the same period, with the coefficient 0.02 being sized so the term has a minimal impact on the optimization.

The following equations describe the energetic constraints, including the evolution of energy stored in the battery, Eq. 4.12, minimum and maximum energy stored, Eq. 4.13, and power constraints, Eq. 4.15, Eq. 4.16. Additionally, to ensure a fair result, it is imposed that the energy has to be the same at the beginning and end of the optimization, Eq. 4.14.

$$C_{BESS,t} = C_{BESS,t-1} \cdot (1 - \tau) + (P_{c,t} + P_{aFFR,down,t}) \cdot \eta_{char} - \frac{(P_{d,t} + P_{aFFR,up,t})}{\eta_{disc}} \quad \forall t \neq 0 \quad \text{Eq. 4.12}$$

$$C_{BESS,max} \cdot SOC_{min} \leq C_{BESS,t} \leq C_{BESS,max} \cdot SOC_{max} \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.13}$$

$$C_{BESS,0} = C_{BESS,tmax} \quad \text{Eq. 4.14}$$

$$0 \leq P_{c,t} + P_{aFFR,down,t} \leq P_{BESS} \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.15}$$

$$0 \leq P_{d,t} + P_{aFFR,up,t} \leq P_{BESS} \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.16}$$

Table 4.6 collects the main parameters of the BESS. The maximum power P_{BESS} and storage capacity $C_{BESS,max}$ are irrelevant due to the formulation, that considers the BESS to be installed in a system with very high demand relative to its power and the BESS is not big enough to affect the markets. The capacity-to-power ratio (or hours) is crucial though.

Table 4.6. BESS common parameters and capacities used.

Round-trip efficiency (AC-AC)	85% [35]
$\eta_{char} = \eta_{disc}$	92.20%
Depth of discharge	80%
SOC _{min} / SOC _{max}	10% / 90%
Self-discharge rate (τ)	0.2 %/day [36]
Cycle life	5,000 [37]
Capacities	1-h, 2-h, 4-h, 8-h

4.3.3. Grid-based optimization

As stated in Section 3.2, the advantages of integrating MPCs into the grid are not limited to the energy distribution but are most important regarding the enhancement of grid operation. For this task, the work presented in [9] has been used.

The aim is to analyse the impacts of installing a MPC on the voltage regulation of reduction of grid losses, and the objective function needs to be changed accordingly. For the former, Eq. 4.17 is created to minimize the voltage deviations across the buses, ensuring voltage stability. For the latter, Eq. 4.18 is applied to minimize the power losses in the network. In the results section, the base case scenario consists of running the AC-optimal power flow (AC-OPF) on the raw grid with the losses objective function.

$$Voltage_OF = \min \left[\sum_{\forall t} \sum_{\forall i} (v_{i,t} - 1)^2 \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4.17}$$

$$Losses_OF = \min \left[\sum_{\forall t} \sum_{\forall k} \sum_{\forall l} (i_{kl,t}^2 \cdot r_{kl}) \cdot S_b \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4.18}$$

For the implementation of the MPCs to the grid, it has been considered that a new line is built parallel to the existing switchable line, with the same parameters. Then, the converter is placed at one end of the line creating a new bus for one terminal and connecting the other to the existing bus.

The power balance within each multiport converter must be ensured by considering the active and reactive powers exchanged by each terminal. This is expressed mathematically by ensuring the sum of active powers exchanged by the terminals of the MPC equals zero at every time step, Eq. 4.19. The power limits are represented by Eq. 4.20 and can be visualised as the circle in Figure 4.4. The reactive power is further limited, considering the IEEE Standard 1547 [38] which recommends that energy storage DER should have a minimum reactive power capability of $\pm 44\%$ of their nominal power, Eq. 4.21.

Figure 4.4. Power limits for each of the ports [38].

$$\sum_{\forall k} p_{mpc,i,t} = 0 \quad \forall t \quad \text{Eq. 4.19}$$

$$p_{mpc,i,t}^2 + q_{mpc,i,t}^2 \leq s_{ni}^2 \quad \forall i, t \quad \text{Eq. 4.20}$$

$$-0.44 \cdot s_b \leq q_{mpc,i,t} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_b \quad \forall i, t \quad \text{Eq. 4.21}$$

4.4. Data representation

Due to the large amount of data needed to be represented, up to 96 hourly values for each of the 33 buses, it has been decided to use boxplots for the graphical representations. Boxplots provide a visual summary of the data, highlighting the median, quartiles, and potential outliers. The default parameters of Matplotlib (a comprehensive library for creating static, animated, and interactive visualizations in Python) have been used [39], represented in Figure 4.5.

Whiskers extend to the maximum and minimum values of the series or up to 1.5 times the Inter Quartile Range (IQR). The box itself represents the IQR, stretching from quartile 1 (Q1) to Q3, with a line inside the box indicating the median of the dataset. Caps are the horizontal lines at the ends of these whiskers, marking the furthest points within the whisker range. Finally, outliers are points plotted individually outside the whiskers.

Figure 4.5 Boxplot example. Own source.

To represent voltage data effectively, mean voltage profiles with standard deviation are used, as shown in Figure 4.6. This method illustrates the average voltage levels and their variability across different buses. The solid line indicates the mean voltage without MPC, and the dashed line shows the mean voltage with MPC. Shaded areas represent the standard deviation, highlighting the consistency of voltage levels.

Figure 4.6. Example of voltage data representation.

5. Results and discussion

By default, in the energy-based optimizations, it has been considered that the DG units are capable of generating despite being isolated from the grid or without an MPC creating it. However, that's not the case for the grid-following optimizations. Additionally, since there is no clear data on line longitudes and fault probabilities or even if the lines are overhead lines or cables, equal fault probability has been considered for all lines, with an annual failure rate considered of 4 hours, for the entire system. The general data for the simulations is collected in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Key costs and project lifetime.

Converter cost (per terminal) [€/kW]	150
Battery cost [€/kWh]	500
Battery O&M cost [€/kWh/year]	7.5
Cost of ENS (C_{ENS}) [€/kWh]	6
Project lifetime [years]	30
Energy bought to the grid [€/MWh]	50

To reduce the computational requirements of the optimization, the number of lines that can fail has been reduced from the total of 32 to 6. These are lines 2, 7, 11, 18, 22, and 25, selected because they are critical lines that would isolate the different bus groupings.

5.1. Expected results

It is possible to estimate when the threshold time beyond which is economically feasible to install an MPC for delivering the energy if it has access to the grid, by matching the cost of the converter and the cost of the ENS, Eq. 5.1:

$$ENS \cdot L_{prj} \cdot C_{ENS} = \sum_i C_{conv-i} \cdot P_{MPC,i} \quad \text{Eq. 5.1}$$

where C_{conv-i} and $P_{MPC,i}$ are the specific cost and power the MPC's terminal i , and ENS the annual energy not supplied, C_{ENS} its cost and L_{prj} the project's lifespan. Assuming the demand to be constant, which is reasonable for short time periods, we can divide it in power times hours. By isolating hours and substituting the relevant parameters, the threshold failure time can be derived, as shown in Eq. 5.2. Note that the cost of the converter is now expressed as two times the cost of one terminal, in this case, there is not a third terminal with renewables or battery. Additionally, the cost of the energy bought to the grid to supply what otherwise would be ENS is neglected, since it is two orders of

magnitude lower than that of the ENS.

$$h = \frac{2 \cdot C_{conv-i}}{L_{prj} \cdot C_{ENS}} = 1h \ 40min \quad \text{Eq. 5.2}$$

Similarly, it is possible to theoretically obtain the values relating to the economic feasibility of installing a battery to supply the demand in case of fault, Eq. 5.3. For the battery OPEX cost, it is frequent to be described as a fraction of the CAPEX, in this case, 1.5%. These costs are described in Eq. 5.4, where P_{BESS} is the power of the battery [kW] h is the number of hours that can deliver energy at that power and B_c the cost in [€/kWh].

Again, supposing the demand to be constant along the faulted hours it is divided in power times hours. On the investment costs side, the MPC should now have three terminals, since it is not possible to know in advance which will be the faulted line. Assuming equal cost and power for each of the i terminals:

$$ENS \cdot L_{prj} \cdot C_{ENS} = \sum_i C_{conv-i} \cdot P_{MPC,i} + C_{bat} \quad \text{Eq. 5.3}$$

$$C_{bat} = CAPEX_{bat} + OPEX_{bat} \cdot 30 = P_{BESS} \cdot h \cdot B_c + P \cdot h \cdot B_c \cdot \frac{1.5}{100} \cdot 30 \quad \text{Eq. 5.4}$$

$$C_{bat} = P_{BESS} \cdot h \cdot B_c \cdot 1.45$$

$$P \cdot h \cdot 30 \cdot 6 = P \cdot (3 \cdot 150 + h \cdot B_c \cdot 1.45) \quad \text{Eq. 5.5}$$

From Eq. 5.5, one can note that the longer the fault duration the more feasible is to install a BESS, since the power electronics cost remains constant. For a fault duration of 4 hours, the B_c would need to be below 47 €/kWh to be feasible. Considering that the current prices for large-scale BESS are around 500 €/kWh, this suggests that under current market conditions, the installation of BESS is not economically viable for reasonable fault durations. Note that the real value would be below 47 €/kWh since this approximation does not consider discharge and converter losses.

5.2. Single line failure

5.2.1. Without closing any switches or installing MPC

Firstly, a simulation is carried out to determine the ENS for a fault at each grid line, without applying any corrective actions to minimize it. This approach helps identify the most critical lines. However, the information provided is limited in scope as the main focus is to understand how the installation of MPC can mitigate the ENS while optimizing its location and power capacity.

Figure 5.1. ENS for single faults at each of the lines.

Figure 5.1 illustrates the ENS for single faults occurring at each of the lines. The boxplot represents the range and distribution of ENS values for faults at various lines, highlighting the most critical ones. The analysis reveals the lines where faults would result in the highest ENS are the ones closer to the main feeder, indicating priority areas for installing MPCs to enhance grid reliability and reduce outages.

5.2.2. Optimal MPC sizing

The installation of MPCs substantially reduces the ENS by providing additional power during fault conditions, ensuring that the energy supply to the grid remains stable and reliable. This is visually evident from the reduced ENS values in the top chart, which aligns with the increased power output from MPCs in the bottom chart, Figure 5.2.

Note that despite the installation of a MPC the ENS is not reduced to 0 but to a small number, this is due to the sizing of the converter being done to avoid covering the peak load of the fault. Out of the 4 hours, the converter will fully supply energy to 3 of them, and the gap between the MPC power and peak load will remain as not supplied, refer to Eq. 5.1.

Figure 5.2. ENS (top) and optimal MPC (bottom) power for 4-hour fault at the selected lines and MPC locations.

Table 5.2 represents the average values for faults in the six selected faulted lines and the four MPC locations. Note that the location that maximizes the installed power is the one with the lower overall costs, meaning that for an annual average of 4 hours of faults is economically advantageous to install an MPC to supply the demand. In particular, location 34 is better than 33 thanks to its ability to supply all the buses in case of a fault at line 11, see Figure 5.2.

Table 5.2. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations.

MPC	ENS [kWh]	C_{BESS} [kWh]	P_{MPC} [kW]	C_{ENS} [€]	C_{MPC} [€]	Total Cost [€]
33	769.66	0.00	406.67	138,539	122,000	260,539
34	622.77	0.00	445.34	112,098	133,603	245,701
35	1,746.18	0.00	155.91	314,312	46,772	361,084
36	1,587.31	0.00	196.97	285,715	59,090	344,805

5.2.3. Grid-following DG approach

As mentioned before, energetic-based simulations don't consider any grid restriction. Most of today's VRES operate in grid-following mode, meaning that they need a strong AC grid to operate. Despite grid operator's requirements for fault ride through, VRES will eventually disconnect to protect themselves if isolated from the grid. Thus, the energy not supplied will be significantly higher than that appointed in previous chapters, improving the economic benefits of installing a solution to supply that demand. The benefits don't come from the extra energy generated by VRES (~80 €/MWh) but from reducing ENS (~6000 €/MWh).

Figure 5.3 represents the ENS in case of grid-following operation of DG and no actions are applied in the normal operation grid configuration. Compared to Figure 5.1, the mean ENS per fault has increased from 1712 kWh to 2373 kWh.

Figure 5.3. ENS for single faults at each of the lines in grid-following DG case.

As mentioned, under this more aligned with reality grid-following operation mode of DG, the penalty for leaving buses isolated from the main grid, or a power electronics element capable of forming the grid, is much higher. This, however, doesn't affect the sizing of the MPC for faults longer than 2 hours since the MPC will be installed anyway and form the grid in system 2. Shorter time durations are studied in Section 5.4.

On the other hand, since its location is fixed it cannot form a grid in buses in system 4, and the impact of DG is not high enough to make it feasible to install an MPC to supply system 3. The cost of the MPC plus battery still outweighs that of the ENS despite in case of having an MPC of relevant power the DG generation would not be lost, thus lowering the required battery and MPC powers. Regarding buses in system 2, the cost of the ENS is high enough to encourage the installation of an MPC capable of supplying the bulk of the

demand, so DG units in system 2 always find the grid already formed.

What is heavily influenced by DG operating in grid-following is the ENS, demand in buses isolated is now not partially supplied by renewable generators. This increases the energy not delivered and consequentially its cost, which could potentially cause a change in the optimal location of the MPC in case of a more irregular demand and DG distribution.

Table 5.3. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations.

MPC	ENS [kWh]	C_{BESS} [kWh]	P_{MPC} [kW]	C_{ENS} [€]	C_{MPC} [€]	Total Cost [€]
33	1,165.57	0.00	406.67	209,802	122,000	331,802
34	898.71	0.00	445.34	161,767	133,603	295,370
35	2,419.21	0.00	155.91	435,458	46,772	482,230
36	2,218.88	0.00	196.97	399,399	59,090	458,489

5.3. Double line failure

5.3.1. Without closing any switches or installing MPC

In this section, a simulation is performed to assess the ENS for double line failures without any corrective measures such as closing switches or installing MPC. Similarly to Section 5.2.1, this analysis helps identify the critical pairs of lines whose simultaneous faults would cause the most significant ENS.

Figure 5.4. ENS for each pair of faulted lines.

Figure 5.4 presents the ENS for each pair of faulted lines. The boxplot illustrates the range and distribution of ENS values for various pairs of lines, indicating the critical pairs that need attention. This information is crucial for optimizing the location and power capacity of MPC installations to mitigate the impact of such faults. The average values are collected in Table 5.4 and indicate that line 2 (as common line in the fault pair) has the highest average ENS of 7.25 MWh, highlighting its criticality in the network.

Table 5.4. Average ENS per common line fault.

Common line failure	2	7	11	18	22	25
ENS [MWh]	7.25	3.56	3.16	3.51	3.70	4.07

5.3.2. Optimal MPC sizing

Similarly to Figure 5.2, Figure 5.5 represents how installing a MPC reduces the ENS. Conversely, now there are some cases in which all the possible locations for the converter are fully isolated from the main grid, such as faults in lines 2 and 18, in these cases, despite the possibility of installing a converter plus a battery the most economical solution is to not supply the energy.

Figure 5.5. ENS (top) and optimal MPC power (bottom) for 4-hour fault at the selected lines and MPC locations.

Table 5.5. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations, double fault grid-forming DG.

MPC	ENS [kWh]	C_{BESS} [kWh]	P_{MPC} [kW]	C_{ENS} [€]	C_{MPC} [€]	Total Cost [€]
33	2,581.08	0.00	423.41	464,594	127,023	591,617
34	2,812.03	0.00	364.56	506,166	109,367	615,533
35	3,500.36	0.00	187.09	630,066	56,126	686,192
36	3,609.80	0.00	158.12	649,764	47,437	697,202

5.3.3. Grid-following approach

The results captured in Figure 5.6, and Table 5.6 and Table 5.7 further confirm the conclusions from the same study for a single line failure: for a 4-hour fault, the grid-following consideration does not affect the converter sizing, despite it increases the energy not delivered substantially.

Figure 5.6. ENS for single faults at each of the lines.

Table 5.6. Average ENS per common line fault.

Common line failure		2	7	11	18	22	25
ENS [MWh]	Grid-forming DG	7.25	3.56	3.16	3.51	3.70	4.07
	Grid-following DG	9.69	4.99	4.59	4.81	5.56	5.49

Table 5.7. Average optimal costs, P_{MPC} and ENS for different MPC locations, double fault grid-following DG.

MPC	ENS [kWh]	C_{BESS} [kWh]	P_{MPC} [kW]	C_{ENS} [€]	C_{MPC} [€]	Total Cost [€]
33	3,719.76	0.00	423.41	669,557	127,023	796,580
34	3,882.85	0.00	364.56	698,913	109,367	808,280
35	4,813.24	0.00	187.09	866,382	56,126	922,509
36	4,999.49	0.00	158.12	899,909	47,437	947,346

5.4. Failure duration and MPC sizing

In this section, the effects of the different time duration of the fault are presented. A single line failure has been considered and a grid-following approach.

For a 1-hour fault differences appear between grid-forming and grid-following approaches, which can affect the optimal sizing. In the latter, the power generation of the DG units isolated is lost without an element capable of forming the grid. Thus, the reduction in ENS is higher than that going through the MPC, encouraging its installation. Conversely, under a grid-forming energetical simulation approach, the generation from the DG units will be delivered to the loads regardless of the presence of a strong grid, and the rest of the energy will not be delivered by the MPC since the fault duration is too short for that being economically advantageous, refer to Eq. 5.2.

This approach is more relevant in the case of isolating a DG of relatively strong power, thus, a fault in line 22 and converter located in position 35 has been studied. Figure 5.7 shows the obtained results with the only restriction that the power of the converter plus the isolated generation needs to be higher than the isolated demand. In this case, the reduction of ENS combined from the MPC and the wind power plant makes the installation of a converter feasible during all the hours with significant generation.

Figure 5.7. Unrestricted grid-following approach for fault at line 22 and MPC in position 35.

However, note that around hour 76 these constraints allow the WPP to supply the load with no converter at all. Essentially, the WPP is working in an undesired grid-forming mode. With this in mind, it has been introduced that the combined power of MPC and DG needs to be higher than 110% of the load (A coefficient in Eq. 4.7), and the MPC power

needs to be at least 40% of the load power (B coefficient in Eq. 4.8). With this realistic approach considered, the installation of the converter remains feasible in most of the cases, effectively preventing energy wastage and ensuring a more reliable operation.

Figure 5.8. A and B coefficient restricted grid-following approach for 1-hour fault at line 22 and MPC in position 35.

With the aforementioned A and B coefficients, a simulation has been carried out to represent how this realistic grid-following approach can be applied in previous sections’ scenarios. The optimization is conducted for a 1-hour fault duration, given that the resolution of the code is based on hourly intervals. This approach is expected to not have any effects on the results for fault durations extending beyond one hour and forty minutes.

Figure 5.9. P_{MPC} for A and B coefficient restricted grid-following approach for 1-hour fault.

Table 5.8 demonstrates how the locations that allow to form the grid in the buses with the most installed capacity DG units are the most benefited by this approach. Location 35, with the ability to form the grid at the bigger generators (located at buses 25 and 33), is

the one with the highest savings-to-investment ratio. However, this does not imply that installing a 26.94 kW MPC at location 35 is a prudent investment if the total duration of faults across all selected lines amounts to just one hour per year; it merely represents the average value. In fact, installing such a converter would not make any impact at all as it would be too small to fulfil the 40% of the load criteria.

Table 5.8. Comparison of grid-following approach between DG lost and DG available if the grid is formed.

	ENS [kWh]	P _{MPC} [kW]	C _{ENS} [€]	C _{MPC} [€]	Total Cost [€]
DG lost case	819.01	0.00	147,422	0	147,422
MPC location					
33	780.27	16.57	140,449	4,972	145,420
34	749.51	28.08	134,912	8,424	143,336
35	749.47	26.94	134,904	8,083	142,986
36	742.46	29.75	133,643	8,925	142,568

5.5. BESS revenue in markets

In previous chapters, the economic feasibility of installing a battery to deliver energy during system faults was studied. This approach requires maintaining the BESS at full charge, ready to act throughout the year, which may not be the most efficient use of the storage capacity. Considering only this revenue source, the cost of the battery (500 €/kWh) plus power electronics (150 €/kW) is much higher than the cost of the ENS ($6 \text{ €/kWh} \cdot L_{\text{prj}}$), Eq. 5.5.

After discarding the energy storage purely as a backup system to limit the energy not supplied, its participation in wholesale electricity markets is analysed in this section, both for energy arbitrage and ancillary services, with the results presented in Table 5.9. It is important to note that, since the objective function remains unchanged for each simulation, the battery might be underused or overused in some cases. Specifically, the cycle penalty, designed to avoid excessive degradation, was calibrated for the 4-hour battery with aFFR participation, ensuring the BESS is replaced once during the project's lifetime.

Figure 5.10. Example of energy arbitrage for a 4-hour battery.

Figure 5.10 represents an example of how the energy arbitrage is done, in the context of not participating in aFFR. Note that the penalty for the battery cycles causes it to remain on standby most of the time, averaging a cycle per day in days with price differences. Remarkably, the average cost of the energy discharged is 107 €/MWh, while that of the charged is 36 €/MWh.

Table 5.9. Economic analysis of BESS with and without aFFR participation.

Battery capacity		1 h	2 h	4 h	8 h
Annual Battery Cycles	With aFFR	512.36	407.6	296.57	182.81
	Without	230.11	218.65	187.07	126.01
Lifespan (years)	With aFFR	9.76	12.27	16.86	27.35
	Without	21.73	22.87	26.73	39.68
Network Revenues (€)	With aFFR	95,597	85,366	68,700	47,841
	Without	82,193	77,705	66,404	46,936
aFFR Revenues (€)	With aFFR	505,664	325,988	180,628	92,883
	Without	-	-	-	-
Total Revenues (€)	With aFFR	601,261	411,354	249,327	140,723
	Without	82,193	77,705	66,403	46,935
CAPEX (€/kWh) [35]	With aFFR	861	537	446	358
	Without	861	537	446	358
CAPEX (€)	With aFFR	15,881,086	7,879,692	4,764,431	2,355,215
	Without	7,132,337	4,226,864	3,005,256	1,623,489
Lifetime profit (€)	With aFFR	5,071,073	4,460,951	2,715,400	1,866,497
	Without	-4,666,540	-1,895,711	-1,013,145	-215,417
Payback (years)	With aFFR	8.59	7.83	10.74	15.26
	Without	N/A (higher than lifespan)			

Despite all BESS being unfeasible with only the revenues from energy arbitrage, represented with not applicable (N/A) values in the payback, it should be noted that for this task the better-suited batteries are the ones with higher Capacity/Power (C/P) ratio, thanks to a lower capacity cost. Even the 8-hour battery is close to achieving a positive lifetime profit. However, considering the project lifespan of nearly 40 years and the lack of consideration for the evolution of money over time or financial costs, the project remains far from being seen as a viable investment.

On the other side, all scenarios are feasible with the participation in aFFR, knowing the results of the markets beforehand. The lower the C/P the higher the revenues are from ancillary services, but the most interesting battery is the 2-hour one, due to the significant increase in cost in the 1-hour.

5.6. Electrical simulation

To assess the potential of MPC in improving grid performance, several cases will be studied, including partial- (300 kVA) and full-scale converters at the four possible locations, all without line failures. The minimum power to be considered a full-scale converter depends on its location and time period, but 1000 kVA has been used for all cases to ensure a fair comparison. Anyhow, since no faulted lines are considered the MPC role is purely grid performance enhancement, and ENS will not be a factor in this assessment. The results are compared to the base case scenario, which consists of running the AC-OPF on the raw grid with the losses objective function.

5.6.1. Potential for voltage regulation

In the base case, voltage drops below 0.95 p.u. in some of the buses. This can be avoided without interrupting the power supply simply by increasing the voltage at the feeder substation, as there is an on-load tap-changing transformer. However, the voltage deviations would still be very high, highlighting the potential to regulate the voltage using a power electronics device such as an MPC.

Voltage profiles for a partial-scale and full-scale MPC at the four possible locations are presented in Figure 5.11 and Figure 5.12, respectively, with comparisons to the base case.

Figure 5.11. Voltage profiles for 300 kVA MPCs compared to normal operation profiles.

Figure 5.12. Voltage profiles for 1000 kVA MPCs compared to normal operation profiles.

For the 300 kVA MPCs (Figure 5.9), the voltage profiles indicate an improvement in voltage regulation, although the impact varies depending on the location of the MPC. Specifically, the voltage profiles show a noticeable reduction in voltage drops, particularly in the segments of the network that are furthest from the feeder substation. The standard deviation of the voltage profiles also decreases, suggesting a more stable voltage level across the network. When the MPC power is increased to 1000 kVA (Figure 5.10), the improvements in voltage profiles become even more pronounced. The voltage levels are closer to the nominal value of 1 p.u., and the standard deviations are significantly lower

compared to the base case and the 300 kVA scenarios.

It is also important to note that the improvement in voltage regulation from having no MPC to installing a 300 kVA MPC is like the improvement observed when increasing the MPC power from 300 kVA to 1000 kVA. However, the converter cost associated with the second case is 7/3 times higher for achieving a comparable level of improvement. This highlights the need for a cost-benefit analysis when considering the power rating of MPCs for voltage regulation, showing that a partial scale is more advantageous for this task.

Table 5.10. Mean voltage and SD for different MPC locations and power ratings.

Power [kVA]	MPC location	Mean voltage [p.u.]	Standard deviation [p.u.]
0	N/A	0.9785	0.0129
300	33	0.9842	0.0105
	34	0.9863	0.0101
	35	0.9844	0.0102
	36	0.9845	0.0109
1000	33	0.9919	0.0074
	34	0.9942	0.0087
	35	0.9921	0.0082
	36	0.9902	0.0088

5.6.2. Potential for loss reduction

The 1.92% of losses under normal operation conditions can be decreased down to 1.37% for the 1000 kVA-MPC 35 case. Considering the annual consumption of 24 GWh, this represents 133 MWh or 11625 € in savings annually, assuming 87.10 €/MWh (average SPOT market price in 2023 in Spain), which would be even higher due to other tariffs and taxes.

Considering the converter cost of 300,000 € and its 30-year lifetime, lifetime line losses savings are higher than the converter's cost. However, the fact that the line losses are lower does not mean that the overall system losses are lower since the internal losses of the converter must be considered too. In this case, the converter's internal losses are likely to outweigh the improvement in line losses. Additionally, other costs associated with the converter, mainly the construction of the new line, could further complicate the feasibility, despite the possibility of replacing the switch in the existing line or the necessity to build a new line anyway which would eliminate this cost. Overall, in a scenario with relatively low base case losses, the investment in an MPC to operate as an SOP is not economically feasible.

Table 5.11. Impact of closing switches and MPC location and size on power line losses.

Switches closed	MPC location	P_{MPC} [kVA]	Power lines losses [%]
None	None	0	1.92
33			1.55
34			1.54
35			1.59
36			1.84
34 & 35			1.31
All			1.20
None	33	300	1.56
		1000	1.47
	34	300	1.53
		1000	1.47
	35	300	1.53
		1000	1.37
	36	300	1.80
		1000	1.80

5.6.3. The impact of batteries

Combining an MPC plus BESS is expected have a positive impact on the technical parameters of the grid, on the line loading and, consequently, losses. Focusing on energy arbitrage, BESS absorbs energy from the grid when prices are low, these low prices appear under low demand periods and/or high penetration of cheap sources, VRES. For that, when BESS is charging line loadings are either low and are increased or high (due to VRES) and BESS absorbs part of them.

On the other hand, BESS discharge under high prices scenario, typically on peak demand periods. In this case, the energy required to import from the main feeder is lower thanks to the injection of energy by the BESS. Considering the relation between active power and voltage in MV and especially LV distribution grids, having a more constant flow of active power should facilitate voltage regulation too.

6. Economic assessment

This chapter presents the budget developed for this thesis, accounting for human resources, equipment, and software used. The human resources costs are based on the labour hours dedicated to the thesis, calculated from the time of enrollment until the final submission date. For a master's thesis worth 15 ECTS, the expected workload is approximately 375 hours. The average hourly rate is 15 €/h, summing up to a total of 5,625.00 €.

Additionally, the electricity costs for running simulations on a laptop with a 45 W power consumption are included. With a total energy consumption of 16.90 kWh and an electricity cost of 0.20 €/kWh, the total cost for electricity is 3.38 €. The laptop used for this project costs 900 € and is assumed to be amortized over 5 years, leading to an annual amortization cost of 180 €. Given the 5-month duration of this project, the total amortization cost is 75 €.

Transportation costs include private car use and public transport for commuting. The private car is used for 600 km with a rate that includes fuel and amortization of 0.22 €/km, totalling 132.00 €, and public transport costs include two tickets at 42.70 €/ticket, totalling 85.40 €.

Table 6.1. Budget for the development of the thesis.

Description	Units	Unit price	Total cost [€]
Labour hours	375	15.00 €/h	5,625.00
Electricity consumption	16.90 kWh	0.20 €/kWh	3.38
Laptop	5 months	15 €/month	75.00
Private car	600 km	0.22 €/km	132.00
Public transport	2 tickets	42.70 €/ticket	85.40
Total			5,920.78
VAT (21%)			1,243.36
Final cost			7,164.14

The cost of accessing literature databases such as IEEE and Elsevier is assumed by the university, as well as the office 365 pack.

Thus, the total cost for the development of this thesis is 5,920.78 €. Including value-added tax (VAT) (21%), the total cost would be 7,164.14 €.

7. Environmental assessment

The two detected sources of CO₂ emissions that are a direct consequence of the development of this work are electricity consumption and transport. During the February 2024 to June 2024 period, emission factors of the Spanish electrical mix were record low thanks to the large amounts of PV and wind generation and the typical mild spring weather that causes a reduction of demand in comparison to summer and winter, with an average daily value of 85 g CO₂e/kWh [40], see Table 7.1.

Table 7.1. Specific emission factors for the Spanish electrical mix from 2019 to June 2024 [40].

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Feb-June 2024
Specific emissions [g CO ₂ e/kWh]	193	145	140	163	122	85

Considering that the average power consumption of the laptop is 45 W, the total hours of work, and the transport-specific emissions of the used transport sources [41], the total emissions of the thesis are collected in Table 7.2.

Table 7.2. Total CO₂ emissions resulting from the development of this thesis.

	Quantity	Specific emissions	Total emissions [kg CO ₂ e]
Electricity consumption	16.90 kWh	85 g CO ₂ e/kWh	1.44
Private car (per commute)	20 km	120 g CO ₂ e/km	2.40
Metro (per commute)	12 km	30 g CO ₂ e/km	0.36
Interurban bus (per commute)	140 km	33 g CO ₂ e/km	4.62
Transport total	30 commutes	N/A	221.40
Total emissions			222.84

Thus, the total emissions for the thesis amount to 222.84 kg CO₂e. This assessment provides a clear picture of the environmental impact associated with the computational and transport activities during the development of this thesis, highlighting that electric emissions are negligible compared to transport and working from home and the use of public transport can help reduce emissions.

Despite the direct emissions associated with the development of this thesis, this research supports the transition towards a cleaner and more sustainable energy system and the contribution may help decarbonize the energy sector in the future.

8. Social and gender equality assessment

The objectives of this thesis align with several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with direct influence on SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) [42]. These goals are supported by promoting innovation in the energy sector and technologies that enhance grid stability with a higher penetration of VRES, which expels more expensive and pollution generation sources from the electric mix. By extension, this benefits the whole society, especially those who face difficulties accessing energy and individuals living in areas where climate change impacts are harsher, often inhabited by economically disadvantaged people. Other indirect consequences of promoting a cleaner grid and reducing CO₂ emissions align with SDG 13 (Climate Action), SDG 14 (Life Below Water), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

Inclusive language and non-sexist, non-androcentric imagery have been used throughout this thesis to ensure gender neutrality and inclusivity. The project does not endorse discriminatory policies based on gender, race, culture, or economic status, advocating for equal access to technological advancements and their benefits for all societal groups.

9. Conclusions

This thesis has explored the potential of MPC to enhance the resilience and performance of distribution grids, focusing on reducing energy not supplied and facilitating the integration of distributed energy resources too. Through a comprehensive literature review, case study design, and detailed simulation, several key findings and implications have emerged.

The work has allowed to spot the most critical lines and optimal locations to counteract the faults at different lines. The analysis of single- and double-line failures without the intervention of switches or MPCs showed substantial amounts of energy not supplied, bigger when considering a more realistic grid-following approach of DG, indicating a clear need for improvements in grid resilience. The optimal sizing of MPCs demonstrated that strategic placement and sizing of these converters could significantly reduce ENS, especially when installed in positions 33 or 34, highlighting their effectiveness in enhancing grid reliability. The use of MPCs is significantly more important if the DG operates in a grid-following mode since these generators disconnect from the grid if the grid disappears.

For the energy-based simulations, no differences appear between a converter and a simple switch, which is indeed much cheaper. However, MPC's advantages are not limited to that and include enhanced grid stability by controlling active and reactive power flow and facilitating the integration of DER avoiding the curtailment of DG and loads. In case of non-constant power throughout the failure, the typical response from the optimization is to size the MPC for the base load during the period, and not supply the rest of the energy.

The study has demonstrated the capabilities of MPCs to regulate voltages and decrease line losses. Based on the analysis presented, it is evident that employing partial-scale MPCs provides a more cost-effective solution, as the improvement from partial-scale to the base case is comparable to that from full-scale to partial-scale. These partial-scale MPCs offer significant improvement in voltage regulation, with noticeable reductions in voltage drops, particularly in network segments farthest from the feeder substation, as well as reductions in losses. Specifically, a 300 kVA MPC at position 34 offers a balanced and cost-effective approach to optimizing grid performance, making it the preferred choice for voltage regulation and loss reduction.

However, it is not possible to deliver all the energy demanded in case of fault if the converter is not at full scale. This suggests that the most cost-effective solution is to have in parallel a partial-scale MPC with the aim of enhancement of power flow and voltage regulation with a switch, that will only close in case of line failure.

Despite the possibility of reducing losses by closing the existing switches and operating the grid in a meshed configuration, this solution is much more challenging than it seems. Distribution networks are built meshed but operated radially to simplify protection coordination and reduce the complexity associated with fault detection and isolation. Thus, the installation of MPCs might be the only viable option to reduce losses without replan the entire network protection scheme.

Regarding the BESS, it seems quite unlikely to be feasible if its only use is to remain on standby as an energy source in case of fault-causing isolation. From its participation in markets, it has been demonstrated that can be feasible, but with the impossible case of knowing the future requirements for participation in the ancillary services. Only for energy arbitrage and considering 2023 Spain's day-ahead prices BESS isn't feasible. However, the costs of the battery could be lower than those used in the results thanks to the ability of MPC to integrate multiple devices, and its revenues could be higher in markets with capacity payments. Additionally, these systems could become more advantageous with supportive legislation that incentivizes monetization, allowing project developers to realize a greater share of the positive impacts their projects have on the grid.

The integration of market participation and backup energy sources remains to be studied. In that case, it should be done considering the probability of faults imposed to have the BESS at full capacity in case of events that could lead to line failures, such as wildfires or thunderstorms.

Future work

The multiple possible configurations of MPC made it impossible to be analysed in the context of this work. The most interesting points that remained out of the scope and are considered a natural and useful continuation are:

- Analyse the reference days selection or increase the number of days used per simulation, in case of having more computational power. Improve the efficiency of the code.
- Analyse the impact of BESS on the electrical parameters of the grid. It is expected to be beneficial to ensure a more constant power flow through the lines, improving voltage regulation and line loadings.
- Include battery degradation in the analyses and quantify how grid-following/grid-forming operation affects the critical battery price for making it profitable.
- Further explore the integration capabilities of MPC, considering for example cases with integration of DG and loads through the MPC.

10. Acknowledgments

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Oriol Gomis, for providing me with the opportunity to work on this project and for his essential guidance throughout the development of this thesis. I am also deeply thankful to my co-supervisor, Paula Muñoz, for the numerous meetings and her assistance with the coding aspects of the project. Additionally, I extend my thanks to all the iPLUG members at CITCEA, from whom I have learned a lot, with a special mention to Marc Cheah, who also offered guidance and support.

This work is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme in the framework of the project "iPLUG" with grant agreement number 101069770.

11. Bibliography

- [1] “L’Acord de París. Canvi climàtic.” Accessed: Jun. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://canviclimatic.gencat.cat/ca/oficina/actuacio_internacional/acord_paris/index.html
- [2] IEA, “World Energy Outlook 2022,” Paris, 2022. [Online]. Available: www.iea.org/t&c/
- [3] I. Renewable Energy Agency, “Renewable capacity statistics 2024,” Abu Dhabi, 2024. [Online]. Available: www.irena.org
- [4] I. Renewable Energy Agency, *Renewable power generation costs in 2022*. 2023. [Online]. Available: www.irena.org
- [5] “Home - iplug-he.eu.” Accessed: Jun. 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://iplug-he.eu/>
- [6] I. Energy Agency, “Electricity 2024 - Analysis and forecast to 2026,” 2024. [Online]. Available: www.iea.org
- [7] “Mathematical Optimization Society.” Accessed: Jun. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mathopt.org/?nav=home>
- [8] D. G. Luenberger, *Linear and nonlinear programming*, Fifth edition. in International series in operations research & management science ; 228. Cham: Springer, 2021.
- [9] Paula Muñoz Peña, “Design and operation of multiport converters for distribution systems,” UPC, Escola Tècnica Superior d’Enginyeria Industrial de Barcelona, 2024.
- [10] “Optimization.” Accessed: Jun. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://mlstory.org/optimization.html>
- [11] “Voltage Source Converters - ENTSO-E.” Accessed: Jun. 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/Technopedia/techsheets/voltage-source-converters>
- [12] K. Mardanimajd, S. Karimi, and A. Anvari-Moghaddam, “Voltage stability improvement in distribution networks by using soft open points,” *International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 155, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.ijepes.2023.109582.

- [13] X. Ge, M. M. Shi, C. Zhang, G. Wenjie, and Z. Fan, "A low-cost hybrid back-to-back soft open point," in *2020 IEEE 1st China International Youth Conference on Electrical Engineering, CIYCEE 2020*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., Nov. 2020. doi: 10.1109/CIYCEE49808.2020.9332640.
- [14] M. Deakin, "OPTIMAL HYBRID MULTIPLEXED AC-DC-AC POWER CONVERTERS," 2023.
- [15] M. Deakin, P. C. Taylor, J. Bialek, and W. Ming, "Design and Operation of Hybrid Multi-Terminal Soft Open Points using Feeder Selector Switches for Flexible Distribution System Interconnection," Jan. 2022, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2201.05817>
- [16] L. Zhang, Y. Chen, C. Shen, W. Tang, and J. Liang, "Coordinated voltage regulation of hybrid AC/DC medium voltage distribution networks," *Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 463–472, May 2018, doi: 10.1007/s40565-017-0324-x.
- [17] European Power Electronics and Drives Association, Politechnika Poznańska, International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference 13 2008.09.01-03 Poznań, and EPE-PEMC 13 2008.09.01-03 Poznań, "Voltage profile support in distribution networks – influence of the network R/X ratio," *2008 13th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference (EPE-PEMC 2008)*, pp. 2510–2515, 2008.
- [18] Q. Zhou and J. W. Bialek, "Generation curtailment to manage voltage constraints in distribution networks," *IET Generation, Transmission and Distribution*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 492–498, 2007, doi: 10.1049/iet-gtd:20060246.
- [19] "Acceso a ficheros | OMIE." Accessed: Jun. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.omie.es/es/file-access-list>
- [20] "Glosario | ESIOS electricidad · datos · transparencia." Accessed: Jun. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.esios.ree.es/es/glosario>
- [21] "Methodology for the dimensioning of the aFRR needs," 2020.
- [22] Red Eléctrica, "Informes del sistema." Accessed: Jun. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sistemaelectrico-ree.es/>
- [23] "REData - Aldia | Red Eléctrica." Accessed: Jun. 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ree.es/es/datos/aldia>

- [24] I. Renewable Energy Agency, *Electricity storage valuation framework: Assessing system value and ensuring project viability*. 2020. [Online]. Available: www.irena.org
- [25] R. Poudineh, T. Jamasb, and Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, *Electricity supply interruptions: sectoral interdependencies and the cost of energy not served for the Scottish economy*. 2017.
- [26] P. Linares and L. Rey, “The costs of electricity interruptions in Spain: Are we sending the right signals?,” *Energy Policy*, vol. 61, pp. 751–760, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.05.083.
- [27] B. Chen, “Fault statistics and analysis of 220-kV and above transmission lines in a southern coastal provincial power grid of China,” *IEEE Open Access Journal of Power and Energy*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 122–129, 2020, doi: 10.1109/OAJPE.2020.2975665.
- [28] M. Bindi, M. C. Piccirilli, A. Luchetta, and F. Grasso, “A Comprehensive Review of Fault Diagnosis and Prognosis Techniques in High Voltage and Medium Voltage Electrical Power Lines,” *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 21. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI), Nov. 01, 2023. doi: 10.3390/en16217317.
- [29] “Pyomo.” Accessed: Jun. 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pyomo.org/>
- [30] “lpopt: Documentation.” Accessed: Jun. 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://coin-or.github.io/lpopt/>
- [31] “HiGHS - High-performance parallel linear optimization software.” Accessed: Jun. 30, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://highs.dev/>
- [32] S. H. Dolatabadi, M. Ghorbanian, P. Siano, and N. D. Hatziargyriou, “An Enhanced IEEE 33 Bus Benchmark Test System for Distribution System Studies,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 2565–2572, May 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2020.3038030.
- [33] Red Eléctrica de España, “Guía descriptiva - Ser proveedor de servicios de balance”, Accessed: Jun. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: www.ree.es
- [34] “Frequency containment reserves (FCR products) - Fingrid.” Accessed: Jun. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.fingrid.fi/en/electricity-market/reserves_and_balancing/frequency-containment-reserves/#technical-requirements
- [35] “Utility-Scale Battery Storage | Electricity | 2023 | ATB | NREL.” Accessed: Jun. 29,

2024. [Online]. Available: https://atb.nrel.gov/electricity/2023/utility-scale_battery_storage
- [36] A. A. Kebede, T. Kalogiannis, J. Van Mierlo, and M. Berecibar, "A comprehensive review of stationary energy storage devices for large scale renewable energy sources grid integration," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 159. Elsevier Ltd, May 01, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112213.
- [37] "LiFePO4 Battery Cycle Life & Durability." Accessed: Jun. 03, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ecotreelithium.co.uk/news/lifepo4-battery-cycle-life-and-durability/>
- [38] *1547.9-2022 - IEEE Guide for Using IEEE Std 1547 for Interconnection of Energy Storage Distributed Energy Resources with Electric Power Systems.*
- [39] "Matplotlib — Visualization with Python." Accessed: May 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://matplotlib.org/>
- [40] "REData - No renovables detalle emisiones CO2 | Red Eléctrica." Accessed: Jun. 30, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ree.es/es/datos/generacion/no-renovables-detalle-emisiones-CO2>
- [41] "Emisiones de CO2 por modos de transporte motorizado | Idae." Accessed: Jun. 30, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.idae.es/en/node/32886>
- [42] "Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible | Programa De Las Naciones Unidas Para El Desarrollo." Accessed: Jun. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.undp.org/es/sustainable-development-goals>